

NEIGHBORHOOD IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF THE STATE

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mahalla" tamoyilini joriy etish va ma'naviy ma'rifiy ishlarni tashkil etish bo'limi
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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada mahalla haqida va mamlakatimizda so'nggi yillarda mahalla institutining takomillashtirishga doir amalga oshirilgan islohotlar haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: mahalla, o'zini o'zi boshqarish, oilani qo'llab-quvvatlash vazirligi, farmon, qaror.

Abstract. This article talks about the neighborhood and about the reforms implemented in our country in recent years to improve the neighborhood institution.

Key words: neighborhood, self-government, Ministry of Family Support, decree, decision.

Mahalla is an administrative-territorial unit in Uzbekistan, a method of self-management specific to the traditions and values of our people. A neighborhood is a small administrative area, but it is a community of people connected by a common way of life, values, traditions, and customs. At different stages of history, the tasks of the neighborhood changed depending on the changes of times and regimes. The main tasks of the neighborhood are: holding ceremonies together, maintaining and beautifying its territory, educating the young generation in a social spirit, ensuring order in community life, establishing control over the implementation of all traditional norms, observing customs and punishing those who violate them and evade public obligations. This is the reason why priority is given to large-scale reforms in our country, first of all, in the neighborhoods, in the life of every person. Indeed, a prosperous and happy neighborhood is a country. The development of neighborhoods is a solid guarantee and foundation of our country's development, our bright future.

It is known that during the past years of independence, the importance of the neighborhoods, which are a unique system of self-management of the population, in the spiritual and economic life of our society is increasing. The neighborhood and its specific aspects, its role as a spiritual and educational

center, the importance of practical work carried out in it, the need to study such issues as the attitude of other nations of the world to the Uzbek neighborhood created. The interest of scientists from advanced countries with developed economies in the Uzbek neighborhood and the fact that they are studying it, they can make an incomparably large contribution of the neighborhood system to the material and spiritual development of society, the manifestation of unique human qualities in this direction, that is, his thoughts on the need to implement the neighborhood system, which is a center of selflessness, mutual help, morality and spirituality, in their societies are worthy of attention. It is known that the neighborhood, according to its nature and activity, is not only a territorial association, but also a social structure, that is, an organizational form of people's lifestyle.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the neighborhood system, which is considered to be the executor of reforms, along with other systems in our country, and extensive work is being carried out in this regard. Efforts to reform the system, the work carried out over the last two years, and the changes these days are aimed at bringing the neighborhood closer to citizens, making it possible for every family to have a cure for their pain, and increasing its attractiveness. The neighborhood system, which has a centuries-old history and is dominated by feelings of community and brotherhood based on mutual trust, social dialogue and joint responsibility, has changed in form and content over the years.

In particular, on February 18, 2020, the head of our state announced "Measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in the society, further support the neighborhood institution, and bring the system of working with family and women to a new level" Such changes deepened in connection with the announcement of the Decree on the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support according to it. Now, the position of the deputy head of the neighborhood for family, women and social-spiritual issues, as well as for landscaping, real estate and entrepreneurship issues has been introduced. The prevention inspector was also announced as the deputy chairman.

In order to further increase the weight of work in this direction, the President's decision "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of working with youth in the neighborhood" adopted on January 19, 2022 and the decision "Family and wife" of March 1, 2022 - the decree "On measures to improve the system of working with girls, supporting the neighborhood and clergy", "On organizing the activities of the Ministry of support of the

neighborhood and clergy", as well as The decisions "On the organization of the activities of the State Committee for Family and Women" without any exception, start a completely new era in the development of these important areas, which occupy a central place in the life of every compatriot.

Also, the concept for 2020/2024 of supporting the activities of citizens' self-governance bodies, developing the neighborhood system, and introducing the principle of "Prosperous and safe neighborhood" in society was developed.

The Presidential Decree "On measures to improve the system of working with family and women, supporting the neighborhood and religious people" (PF-81, 01.03.2022) was adopted. According to the decree, the chairman of the neighborhood was given additional rights. The chairman of the neighborhood, including the district (city) mayor's assistant, youth leader and women's activist in the neighborhood, to the high-ranking organizations of the above-mentioned employees on the promotion of prevention (senior) inspectors of the base of internal affairs bodies or the application of punitive measures against them up to dismissal from the position they hold may make submissions that are mandatory. It is envisaged that the draft law "On neighborhood" will be developed by July 1, 2022.

As a result of the above reforms implemented in our country, we can see that the functions and tasks of the neighborhood have significantly changed and improved in the next period. After all, the future, prospects and development of the country are closely related to the prosperity and beauty of neighborhoods.

There is no doubt that such an approach to work with neighborhoods on a new basis, to pay proper attention to our society's bright and elderly people, will bring the intended result and fully realize the idea of "for human dignity". Why, everything is clearly defined in the adopted new program documents, practical mechanisms are carefully thought out.

Now the neighborhood institute is being given wide rights and powers, necessary material and technical capabilities, in accordance with the mutually important tasks assigned to it. Neighborhoods are becoming the hot spot of life, change and reforms. From the lowest level, serious attention is paid to the development of many areas and directions, such as comprehensive solution of the problems of the population, creation of new jobs, reduction of crime, quality education and upbringing of the young generation.

In this regard, the chairpersons of the community assemblies have been given important powers, which undoubtedly will serve to increase their reputation among our people and the community. Let's say that the chairman of

the neighborhood is designated as the person responsible for coordinating the activities of the local governor's assistant, women's activist, youth leader, prevention inspector in a mutually cooperative and harmonious way. allows to achieve more practical results.

Starting the work at the lowest level, having the leaders and activists at the republican and regional level, first of all, in remote areas, will have a good effect - this is a fact that has been proven again and again in our next five years of life.

In conclusion, it should be said that the measures aimed at the fundamental reform of the neighborhood system in our country today will not fail to give positive results in the future. Because the neighborhood embodies the high thinking, customs and traditions of our ancestors, and is a reflection of our noble values that are envied by the people of the world. Today, giving a new meaning to this unique structure is of crucial importance in glorifying human dignity, making people happy with life, and confidently moving towards the future.

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